

Nonlinear Dynamics of Hair Cells in the Amphibian Papilla

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Abstract. Hair cells play a crucial role in the mechanics of hearing, performing the first step in the active detection of sound. *Ex vivo* studies of living hair cells therefore provide an important tool for understanding sound detection in the auditory system. In this study, we focus on the nonlinear dynamics of hair bundle oscillations. We develop a robust *ex vivo* preparation of an auditory organ (amphibian papilla) and observe spontaneous oscillations of hair bundles. The observed oscillations generally fall into one of three classes: regular oscillators, bursting oscillators, and spiking oscillators. The regular oscillators have stable oscillations with a clear dominant frequency. The bursting oscillators have stable oscillations interrupted by quiescent regimes. The spiking oscillators are quiescent most of the time, while occasionally performing a brief oscillation. We propose a simple phenomenological model to explain these dynamical regimes.

INTRODUCTION

The frog auditory system includes the sacculus – a low-frequency vibration detector, the basilar papilla – a high-frequency sound detector, and the amphibian papilla (AP) – the low- to mid-frequency sound detector and discriminator. The latter is the main auditory endorgan in amphibians and is the subject of this study. From the examination of the auditory afferent fibers, the AP has been shown to have sharp tuning ($Q_{10\text{dB}} = 4 - 5$) to a wide range of frequencies (100 – 1200 Hz), in contrast to saccular afferent fibers, which are broadly tuned ($Q_{10\text{dB}} = 0.5 - 1.0$) to a much narrower frequency range (20 – 120 Hz). Similar results have been observed by examining the electrical tuning of the hair cells of these endorgans. In addition to this, the AP displays tonotopy along its longer axis, with the rostral end mostly tuning to the lower frequencies (> 100 Hz), while the caudal end tunes to the higher frequencies (< 1200 Hz). The difference in frequency tuning is also accompanied by variability in the hair cells' size, shape, bundle architecture, and membrane electrical properties [1].

While the AP has been extensively studied electrophysiologically, little is known about its mechanical properties. In this study, we develop a robust *ex vivo* preparation of the bullfrog AP and examine its spontaneous oscillations. This semi-intact preparation constitutes one of the very few *ex vivo* preparations of an auditory endorgan in which spontaneous oscillations have been observed [2], and, to the best of our knowledge, the only one in which they have been observed directly without mechanically loading the cell. Spontaneous oscillations are one of the signatures of an active process in a hair cell bundle. Understanding the mechanisms powering these oscillations can provide insight into the underlying nonlinear dynamics of auditory hair cells.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experiments were performed on the isolated AP of the frog *Rana catesbeiana*. Animals were anesthetized (pentobarbital: 150 mg/kg), pitched, and decapitated following protocols approved by the University of California, Los Angeles Chancellor's Animals Research Committee. The membranous labyrinth was removed and immersed in oxygenated artificial perilymph (composition in mM: NaCl, 108; KCl, 2; CaCl₂, 0.25; D-(+)-glucose, 3; HEPES, 5; creatine, 1; sodium pyruvate, 1, pH 7.27). The AP was then excised and digested for 9 min in perilymph containing collagenase IV (Sigma-Aldrich) 15 g/ml at room temperature. The endorgan was then washed free of the enzyme and dissected further to expose the sensory epithelium. The tectorial membrane was carefully removed to expose the hair bundles. The preparation was glued to a coverslip, fixed in the experimental chamber, and mounted on the stage of an upright optical microscope (Olympus BX51WI). Some steps of the preparation are depicted in Fig. 1.

The tissue was imaged through a water-immersion objective (Olympus LUMPlanFL N 60X, NA:1.00) using a high-speed camera (ORCA-Flash4.0 CMOS) at 1000 frames per second. The resulting images have a resolution of 108.3 nm/px. The hair bundle displacement was then extracted from the recordings using customized software in MATLAB.

FIGURE 1. (A) The membranous labyrinth of the frog extracted and immersed in artificial perilymph. (B) The AP separated from neighboring tissues. (C) The dissected tissue is glued to a coverslip and mounted on the stage of the microscope. The scale bar represents $500\ \mu\text{m}$. (D) Image of a hair bundle. The scale bar represents $5\ \mu\text{m}$.

The software calculates the centroid of the intensity of a region of interest, which defines the position of the bundle for the given frame. This calculation is repeated for each frame, yielding a time series of the bundle positions. This procedure allows us to detect displacements as small as $1/200$ of a pixel, which corresponds to $0.54\ \text{nm}$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three Classes of Oscillators

Measurements obtained from hair cells of the AP indicate a large variation in the character of spontaneous oscillations. Among all of the observed spontaneous oscillations, we have identified three classes of oscillators: regular oscillators, bursting oscillators, and spiking oscillators. The regular oscillators have a stable oscillation with a well-defined dominant frequency, ranging from 1 to 90 Hz. The bursting oscillators seem to have two stable regimes: an oscillatory regime akin to the regular oscillators, and a quiescent regime in which no oscillatory dynamics can be observed. Lastly, the spiking cells are mostly placed in a quiescent regime with rare singular oscillations. Representative oscillations from each class of behaviors are displayed in Fig. 2.

FIGURE 2. The scale bars for displacement correspond to $20\ \text{nm}$ on all panels. The scale bars for time are $0.5\ \text{s}$ except for the insert where it is $0.1\ \text{s}$. (A) Regular oscillators. The insert is the zoomed version of the top trace. (B) Bursting oscillators. (C) Spiking oscillators.

Phenomenological Model

We aim to develop a simple model that captures all the general features of the hair bundle dynamics observed in our experiments. For the regular oscillators, the dynamics can be described by a stable limit cycle, whereas for the bursting oscillators, a stable limit cycle should coexist with a stable fixed point. These features can be observed in the

system with a supercritical and a subcritical Hopf bifurcation respectively. One possible mechanism for generating the spiking dynamics could entail the presence of a saddle node on an invariant circle (SNIC) bifurcation, with additive noise-inducing phase slips in the system. A plausible model that can exhibit all three regimes is shown in Eq. (1).

$$\dot{z} = (\mu + i\omega_0)z - |z|^2z - \gamma|z|^4z + F_0 + \eta_t \quad (1)$$

Here $z = x(t) + iy(t)$, where $x(t)$ is the hair bundle displacement. μ , ω_0 , γ , and F_0 are control parameters and η_t is time-dependent noise. The linear and cubic terms derive from the normal form of the supercritical Hopf bifurcation, where the quintic term is introduced to obtain the subcritical Hopf bifurcation. The addition of a constant offset yields a SNIC bifurcation, once the offset overpowers the innate oscillations on the limit cycle. The noise term could function both as the switch between the stable fixed point and the stable limit cycle in the subcritical Hopf regime and as the driver of the spiking oscillations in the SNIC regime.

We propose that this simple model captures the three regimes of active motility observed experimentally. Detailed experimental verification of the model and test of the parameter regimes that determine these classes of behaviors await future studies. We will also consider alternative models that produce comparable dynamics, such as a nonisochronous Hopf oscillator [3] and a Hopf oscillator with feedback on the control parameter [4].

CONCLUSION

We developed a robust *ex vivo* preparation of an auditory organ (amphibian papilla) and observed spontaneous oscillations of hair bundles. Thus far, most of the prior studies of hair bundle dynamics, including measurements of negative hair-bundle stiffness [5] and power law response to sinusoidal stimulation [6], have been performed on the frog's sacculus. Our preparation will allow us to test whether these results generalize to an auditory system. The AP's tonotopy, sharp tuning, relatively thin tectorial membrane, and easier access to innervating neurons are just some of the many properties, that make this preparation well-suited for future studies.

In this study, we identified three classes of spontaneous oscillations and proposed a simple phenomenological model to describe the observed dynamics. In future work, we aim to test this model by measuring the hair bundle's response to mechanical stimulus, as well as the effects of varying ionic concentrations in the artificial perilymph. We will explore whether any substantive differences in hair bundle dynamics arise in the caudal versus the rostral end of the AP.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Anthony Peng]: There was a nice paper on a new frog preparation to measure hair bundle oscillations. I am curious as to whether this is similar to the sacculus 2 chamber preparation and what the orientation of the hair bundles is. From the images, it looks like you are looking at the bundles from the side. Is this because of the nature of the AP or is it similar that you often look from the top down, like in the sacculus?

[Dzmitry Vaido]: This is correct, Figure 1(d) is indeed a side view of the bundle. Unlike the sacculus, the amphibian papilla has some intrinsic curvature which is why we can sometimes see the cells from a side as well as from the top within the same preparation. We have selected a side view of the cell for this figure since it makes it easier to see the morphological features of the hair bundle such as the stereocilia and the kinociliary bulb. However, when we record the hair-bundle dynamics, like the ones you see in Figure 2, we typically use the top view as it makes it easier to track the bundle motion.

[Julius Kraut]: Hi Dzmitry, thank you for this interesting paper! Your data for the 3 different oscillators looks very nice! It got me thinking, what do you think is the benefit of having these 3 different oscillators? Do you think it's just due to biological variation in the parameters of each hair bundle? I have 2 more questions, how does the ex vivo sample preparation affect the results? And what is y in your equation? Is it the phase of the hair bundle displacement? Best, Julius.

[Dzmitry Vaido]: Hi Julius, thank you for these questions!

We observe all three types of oscillations even in neighboring cells so I think it is safe to assume that some internal parameters control what is the state of a given cell. We do not know what those parameters are at this stage, but we plan to examine this further in our future work. We do, however, see this diversity much more in the amphibian papilla than in the sacculus, so it might be beneficial for hearing, but we will have to do more work to understand this better.

Our dissection does change the system quite substantially. We remove the tectorial membrane which decouples the cells, we replace the endolymph and the perilymph with an artificial ionic solution, and we cut the innervation and the blood supply to the tissue. All of these interventions likely affect our measurements, but we have some ideas about how to study those effects. For example, we could use artificial membranes to study the effects of coupling and do experiments similar to the work by Lin and Bozovic (2020) to understand the effects of efferent innervation.

The imaginary component in the equation above captures different hidden variables that we do not have experimental access to. In practice, we can obtain it by applying the Hilbert transform to the displacement.